

Analyzing Effects of Cell to Chassis Technology on Road Noise of Skateboard-Sharing Vehicles

Abstract. While most Noise, Vibration, and Harshness (NVH) research on electric vehicles (EVs) focuses on conventional Cell-to-Pack (CTP) systems, the impact of Cell-to-Chassis (CTC) structures remains under-explored. A concern is that CTC architectures may compromise NVH due to the absence of a dedicated floor panel. This study investigates this concern using a comprehensive methodology: theoretical static stiffness analysis, finite element (FE) dynamic stiffness modeling, in-vehicle stiffness testing, and road noise measurements (60 km/h, rough asphalt). Simulations show the CTC structure is 20 times stiffer than a conventional CTP floor system across the 20-300 Hz frequency range, consistent with theory. Experimental in-vehicle tests reveal no correlation between local dynamic stiffness and interior noise peaks in the primary road noise frequency range (20-300 Hz). This research validates an effective simulation method for floor stiffness and demonstrates that the CTC structure's high dynamic stiffness enables cost and weight reductions by eliminating the need for traditional floor ribs and damping layers.

Keywords: Cell to Chassis, Dynamic Stiffness, Road Noise, Electric Vehicle.

1 Introduction

The pursuit of extended EV range has driven battery pack evolution from Module-to-Pack (MTP) to integrated designs. The first step, CTP, eliminates modules and bolts the pack to the body, fundamentally altering NVH pathways [1]. The latest advance, CTC and CTB, deepens this integration by transforming the pack itself into a load-bearing floor panel—a key distinction from CTP. This architecture offers significant gains in energy density, weight, and cost, with research showing CTB can increase global vehicle stiffness by over 50%, profoundly altering structural dynamics [2]. While classic NVH sources like tire/road noise are well-studied [3-8], the specific acoustic and vibrational consequences of this deep structural integration remain less explored.

In CTC and CTB architectures, the battery acts as a structural component, replacing the separate floor panel of CTP designs. This integration raises acoustic concerns, yet their NVH implications—particularly the local dynamic stiffness of the integrated floor—remain critically under-researched.

This paper is structured to address this gap. First, a theoretical comparison of local static stiffness is conducted for three configurations (a single-layer floor, a floor-CTP system, and a CTC structure) using second moment of area principles. Next, FE models are developed to simulate the local dynamic stiffness of each configuration. Finally, experimental validation is performed through in-vehicle local dynamic

stiffness and road noise measurements. These tests qualitatively evaluate the CTC floor by correlating its dynamic stiffness with interior noise spectra within the primary 20–300 Hz road noise frequency range. The remainder of this paper details these methods, presents the comparative results, and discusses the implications for vehicle NVH design.

2 Structural Configuration and Simplification

To investigate its structural implications, a comparative analysis of three distinct floor configurations was performed, each standardized to 2.5 m by 1.5 m dimensions:

Single-Layer Floor (traditional ICE Architecture): This baseline is the structural steel floor from a traditional ICE vehicle, which lacks an integrated battery. For analysis, it is modeled as a single 1 mm-thick steel plate.

Floor-CTP System: This system comprises a conventional floor panel fastened over a separate CTP battery pack. While the pack is bolted peripherally to the body frame, the central floor is left with only discontinuous support across an 8-10 mm air gap, a design that inherently degrades its local dynamic stiffness. For theoretical analysis, the system is simplified to a 1 mm steel floor and a 150 mm pack component, with its intermittent connections omitted.

Inverted-Cell CTC Architecture: This design directly bonds battery cells via their flat bottoms to the top cover, which also serves as the vehicle floor. This creates a monolithic, highly rigid load-bearing structure with its terminals and valve oriented downwards (Fig. 1). For theoretical analysis, this entire assembly is simplified to a single 150 mm-thick component.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the inverted-cell architecture.

3 Structure-borne Noise Analysis

3.1 Theoretical Calculation: Local Static Stiffness

The local static stiffness or deflection response of a structure are basically governed by its second moment of area, Young's modulus and the point position [9], the local static stiffness is directly proportional to the flexural rigidity. Therefore, a higher second moment of area results in greater resistance to bending and deformation under vertical load.

The resistance of a structural element to bending is quantified by its flexural rigidity, which is the product of Young's modulus and the second moment of area [9]. Local static stiffness is directly proportional to this value; therefore, a larger second moment of area yields a stiffer structure that is more resistant to deformation under a given load.

For a plate clamped on all four edges, the static stiffness at the center is given by [9]:

$$K_s = Eh^3 / (12(1 - \nu^2)\alpha b^2) \quad (1)$$

$$I = bh^3 / 12 \quad (2)$$

Where: K_s is the local static stiffness; E is Young's modulus; h is the plate thickness; ν is Poisson's ratio; α is a dimensionless coefficient dependent on the aspect ratio a/b (for this analysis, $\alpha = 0.00808$); a and b are the plate length and width, respectively. And I is second moment of area. These equations provide a theoretical framework for quantitatively comparing the stiffness of different structural designs based on their cross-sectional geometry.

Fig. 2 presents schematic cross-sections of the three floor configurations analyzed in this study: Traditional single-layer floor: Represents a typical panel from an ICE vehicle (Fig. 2a); Floor-CTP System: Features a 10 mm air gap between the floor panel and the CTP module, which is sealed at the perimeter (Fig. 2b); Inverted-cell CTC structure, where the battery's top cover serves as the integrated vehicle floor.

Fig. 2. Schematic cross-sections comparing the three analyzed floor configurations: (a) conventional single-layer ICE floor; (b) floor-CTP system; and (c) inverted-cell CTC structure.

Table 1 summarizes the key structural properties calculated for the three configurations based on their simplified geometries. The results reveal a stark contrast: the monolithic design of the inverted-cell CTC structure yields a second

moment of area of 421875000 mm⁴, a value over three million times greater than that of the other two configurations (125 mm⁴). Consequently, its calculated central static stiffness demonstrates a proportional increase, being over thirty thousand times greater. It should be noted that these calculations are based on simplified geometries, intentionally omitting the localized effects of bolts and sealant in the floor-CTP system to focus on the fundamental structural differences.

Table 1. Theoretically calculated second moment of area and central static stiffness for the three distinct floor configurations.

Configuration	Young's modulus	Poisson's ratio	Second moment of area	Central static stiffness
ICE 1- layer floor	210 GPa	0.3	125 mm ⁴	1 N/mm
EV CTP floor	210 GPa	0.3	125 mm ⁴	1 N/mm
EV CTC	2 GPa	0.3	421875000 mm ⁴	34001 N/mm

The CTC architecture's substantially higher second moment of area directly yields enhanced local static stiffness. This is a fundamental factor for mitigating structure-borne road noise, as a stiffer structure is inherently less susceptible to vibratory excitation and subsequent noise radiation.

To evaluate the effect of stiffening ribs—a conventional method for enhancing rigidity in ICE and standard EV structures—on the inherently stiff CTC architecture, the flat panel in each configuration was replaced with a ribbed panel (Fig. 3). The ribs were defined with a 3 mm height and 30 mm width, symmetrically arranged, with all other geometric parameters held constant.

Fig. 3. Cross-sectional comparison of the two panel designs evaluated: (a) the baseline flat panel and (b) the stiffened corrugated panel.

Table 2 presents the calculated properties for the stiffened corrugated configurations. A comparison with the baseline results in Table 1 reveals that the addition of ribs yields a substantial increase (approximately 50-fold) in the second moment of area for both the single-layer and floor-CTP systems. In stark contrast, the same modification results in only a marginal 0.5% improvement for the already rigid CTC architecture. The calculated static stiffness follows an identical trend. However, it is important to acknowledge a key simplification in this analysis. For modeling purposes, the entire Cell-to-Chassis (CTC) assembly was represented as a single, isotropic material with a

Young's modulus of 2 GPa. This simplified assembly consisted of the CTC frame, adhesive and a homogenized battery cell, which was used to represent the cell's inherently complex and layered internal structure (cathode, anode, etc.). Consequently, the calculated stiffness for the CTC structure likely represents an overestimation, and the actual performance gap between it and the conventional floors may therefore be less pronounced than these results suggest.

Table 2. Theoretical second moment of area and central static stiffness for the three floor configurations incorporating a ribbed panel design

Configuration	Rib height	Rib width	Second moment of area	Central static stiffness
ICE 1-layer floor	3 mm	30 mm	6238 mm ⁴	53 N/mm
EV CTP floor	3 mm	30 mm	6238 mm ⁴	53 N/mm
EV CTC	3 mm	30 mm	424089900 mm ⁴	34179 N/mm

3.2 Finite Element Analysis: Local Dynamic Stiffness

While static stiffness describes a structure's response to a constant load, dynamic stiffness provides a more complete characterization of its behavior under vibratory conditions. It is a frequency-dependent property that incorporates not only the static stiffness but also inertial and damping effects. The relationship, as presented in [10], is given by:

$$K_d = K_s - m\omega^2 + i\omega c \quad (3)$$

Where the terms are defined as:

K_d is the frequency-dependent dynamic stiffness

K_s is the static stiffness

m is the mass

c is the damping coefficient

ω is the angular frequency

i is the imaginary unit

For complex geometries where analytical solutions are impractical, FEA is the preferred method for predicting dynamic stiffness.

To conduct a higher-fidelity numerical investigation, we employed the commercial FEA solver, OptiStruct, to perform a detailed frequency response analysis. The primary metric of interest was the vertical dynamic stiffness, defined as the frequency-dependent transfer function between an applied force and the resulting displacement.

To ensure a controlled and meaningful comparison, this stiffness was computed at an identical point within the driver's footwell—a typical area critical for road noise transmission. As illustrated by their respective cross-sections in Fig. 4, the three configurations evaluated were: (a) the traditional ICE floor, reinforced by a longitudinal beam; (b) the conventional EV floor, positioned with a 10 mm clearance above the CTP; and (c) the inverted-cell CTC structure, where the top cover functions integrally as the vehicle floor.

Fig. 4. Cross-sectional schematics of three floor configurations modeled for FEA dynamic stiffness analysis: (a) traditional ICE floor, (b) Floor-CTP system, and (c) inverted-cell CTC.

The material properties and physical parameters adopted for the FEA modeling are comprehensively listed in Table 3. A critical modeling decision involved the representation of the battery cells, whose internal structure is a complex, layered composite of materials including the anode, cathode, separator, and electrolyte. Given the focus of this study on macroscopic structural behavior and the need for computational tractability, a necessary simplification was employed: the entire cell was modeled as a single, homogeneous, and isotropic solid. The Young's modulus for this simplified material was determined to be 2 GPa. This value was derived by correlating the simulation model with the results of a physical battery pack vibration test.

Table 3. Material properties used for the FEA of the three floor configurations.

Material	Young's modulus	Density	Poisson's ratio	Damping coefficient
ICE 1- layer floor	210 GPa	7850 kg/m ³	0.3	0.06
EV CTP floor	210 GPa	7850 kg/m ³	0.3	0.06
EV CTP frame	210 GPa	7850 kg/m ³	0.3	0.06
EV CTC frame	210 GPa	7850 kg/m ³	0.3	0.06
Battery cell	2 GPa	2200 kg/m ³	0.3	0.06

The simulation results (Fig. 5) reveal stark differences in dynamic stiffness. The CTC architecture's stiffness is substantially higher—on average 20 times greater—across the 20-300 Hz range. In contrast, the ICE and CTP floors fluctuate between 80 and 200 N/mm, but the CTP system is notably weaker, exhibiting several low-frequency resonant valleys that indicate high susceptibility to structure-borne noise. This underperformance, consistent with theory, is attributed to CTP's packaging constraints, which prevent the use of effective stiffening beams found in the ICE architecture. Conversely, the monolithic CTC structure maintains its high stiffness without significant resonant valleys, minimizing its vibratory response to road

excitation.

Fig. 5. FEA-predicted local dynamic stiffness in the driver's footwell region for the three distinct floor configurations.

3.3 Finite Element Analysis : Road Noise

To isolate and precisely quantify the specific acoustic influence of the CTC's structural integration, a meticulously controlled comparative FEA was devised and executed. Our investigation began with the baseline full-vehicle FE model, which accurately represents the fully integrated state of the CTC architecture. This model explicitly features the strong, continuous adhesive bond that monolithically joins the top cover to the underlying battery cells (Fig. 6a). To create a direct counterpart model that emulates the dynamic behavior of a vehicle with a floor-CTP system, a single, critical modification was made. The adhesive bond was computationally suppressed, which effectively severs the primary structural load path between the cover and the cell, thereby decoupling the two components into distinct bodies (Fig. 6b). This rigorous "A-B" comparative methodology is crucial because it eliminates all other potential confounding variables, ensuring that any observed differences in the

simulated interior road noise can be causally and unambiguously attributed solely to the presence or absence of this critical structural integration.

Fig. 6. FEA models showing (a) the integrated CTC structure with its adhesive bond, and (b) the same structure with the bond removed to emulate a decoupled Floor-CTP system.

A full-vehicle FE model evaluated each floor's contribution to road noise, predicting sound pressure at the driver's ear from measured tire-road excitation during a 60 km/h drive (Fig. 7). The CTC structure provides a significant acoustic advantage below 70 Hz and at 120 Hz, with a maximum reduction of 10 dB at 28 Hz—the primary resonance frequency of the more flexible Floor-CTP system. This finding necessitates countermeasures, such as stiffening ribs and damping layers, to mitigate the inherent vulnerability of conventional EV floors. Key design objectives are to maximize the floor's dynamic stiffness while offsetting its modal frequencies from other major radiating panels, like the firewall and roof.

Fig. 7. Comparison of simulated interior road noise for the CTC and Floor-CTP systems at (a) the driver's location and (b) the rear passenger's ear location.

4 In-Vehicle Experiment

4.1 In-Vehicle Experiment :Local Dynamic Stiffness

To measure the local dynamic stiffness, two distinct floor architectures—the conventional floor-CTP system and the CTC structure—were evaluated using impact hammer testing in an acoustic laboratory. The experimental setup (Fig. 8) included: (1) a Siemens Simcenter Testlab SCADA system for processing Frequency Response Functions (FRFs); (2) an instrumented impact hammer; and (3) an accelerometer mounted adjacent to the impact point.

Fig. 8. Schematic diagram of experimental setup.

Since road noise is dominated by the floor's normal vibration in its weakest regions, measurements were concentrated in the central footwalls. To measure local dynamic stiffness, driving point FRFs were acquired by impacting adjacent to a tri-axial accelerometer, using the normal (Z-axis) response. The specific sensor layouts for each configuration are detailed in Fig. 9. For the floor-CTP system, the sensor was mounted on the floor panel (Fig. 9a), while for the CTC structure, it was affixed directly to the battery cover (Fig. 9b).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9. Local dynamic stiffness measurements in footwell regions for both the (a) floor-CTP system and (b) CTC structure.

The measured local dynamic stiffness results are presented in Fig. 10. The inverted-cell CTC structure exhibits a consistently high local dynamic stiffness, averaging approximately 2000 N/mm over the critical 50-200 Hz frequency range. In stark contrast, the conventional floor-CTP system demonstrates a significantly lower stiffness of approximately 100 N/mm and is characterized by several pronounced stiffness valleys at 135, 175, and 250 Hz, where values drop below 60 N/mm. These low-stiffness points indicate a high susceptibility to road-induced vibrations. This disparity means that for an identical force input, the CTC structure's velocity response is approximately 1/20 that of the floor-CTP system.

Fig. 10. Experimental comparison of local dynamic stiffness for the CTC structure versus the conventional floor-CTP system.

4.2 In-Vehicle Experiment: Road Noise

To validate simulations and demonstrate the CTC architecture's real-world benefits, vehicle-level road noise measurements were conducted on a rough asphalt road providing broadband excitation in the 20-300 Hz structure-borne noise range. While this excitation affects both the CTC and flexible body panels (e.g., roof, tailgate), the CTC's local stiffness—typically 20 times greater—makes it behave as a relatively rigid body. Consequently, these more flexible surfaces, not the CTC structure itself, act as the primary acoustic radiators generating interior noise.

A direct vehicle-level road noise comparison is impractical for two primary reasons. First, the vehicles have significant structural differences beyond the floor, such as in their beams. Second, dominant noise from other panels (e.g., windscreens) masks the floor's contribution, particularly that of the ultra-stiff CTC structure.

Consequently, testing was confined to the CTC vehicle, with the objective shifting from direct comparison to correlating its dynamic stiffness with road noise performance.

Fig. 11 presents the interior road noise results at constant 60 km/h. Spectra at the driver's and rear passenger's ears show similar resonant frequencies, differing primarily in amplitude; a peak near 25 Hz, for example, is attributed to the tailgate's rigid mode. The road noise peaks do not align with the dynamic stiffness valleys of the CTC structure (Fig. 10). This lack of correlation confirms the CTC structure is not a primary road noise contributor, a result of its exceptionally high stiffness.

Fig. 11. Road noise measured in a skateboard-sharing vehicle on a rough asphalt road.

5 Conclusions

This paper analyzes the local dynamic stiffness of a novel CTC structure against a floor-CTP system and a single-layer ICE floor. Static stiffness was first derived theoretically from fundamental parameters using the second moment of area. Dynamic behavior was then investigated using FEA, which incorporated detailed material and geometric properties. This FEA approach identified dynamic stiffness valleys due to resonances and enabled a controlled road noise comparison between the CTC and floor-CTP systems. Finally, local stiffness and vehicle-level road noise tests were conducted to validate the numerical predictions. The following general conclusions can be drawn:

- (1) Theoretical calculations based on the second moment of area strongly correlated with FEA results. While the theoretical approach offers a rapid method for predicting static stiffness from geometry, FEA provides a more comprehensive and accurate analysis of the structure's dynamic stiffness.

- (2) The CTC architecture provides superior local dynamic stiffness, yielding a significant road noise advantage. This stems from its inverted-cell design, which bonds cells directly to the battery cover to form a monolithic, load-bearing structure. In contrast, the floor-CTP system is more prone to road noise, as its underlying pack eliminates the design space for effective stiffening beams—a packaging constraint absent in ICE architectures.
- (3) CTC's high intrinsic stiffness eliminates the need for traditional floor stiffeners and damping layers on floor, offering possible significant weight and cost savings. These countermeasures, however, remain essential for mitigating low-frequency road noise in ICE and CTP-based EVs.

The inverted-cell CTC architecture provides a significant improvement in local dynamic stiffness over conventional designs, though the models presented rely on key simplifications. Future work should incorporate more realistic orthotropic material models and include internal crash-safety voids, both of which would refine modal predictions. Furthermore, as the analysis was confined to the battery-occupied region, a full-vehicle simulation is the logical next step. This system-level investigation is necessary to fully quantify the NVH benefits and dynamic interactions of the highly integrated CTC architecture.

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